

PREVENTING AND COMBATING CORRUPTION-RELATED OFFENSES IS THE GUARANTEE OF THE COUNTRY'S FUTURE

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Abstract: This article examines the opinions of legal scholars on the topic of preventing and combating corruption offenses as a guarantee of the country's future, and the author develops proposals and recommendations.

Keywords: corruption, corruption offenses, society, state, governance.

Corruption is a vice that hinders the implementation of fundamental reforms in all spheres of the state's social life, leads to violations of human rights and freedoms, undermines the normal functioning and mechanisms of public institutions, creates distrust in society towards state power and poses a threat to the country's security. It also negatively affects the country's financial, economic, social, and political life, reduces the effectiveness of public administration and entrepreneurship, worsens the investment climate, and creates social inequality.

It should be noted that the fight against corruption, which is the decline of the state's future, is one of the pressing problems not only in our country but also at the international level.

It is worth mentioning that the word "corruption" comes from the Latin word "corruptio," which means "to buy" or "bribe"[1]. The United Nations Convention against Corruption states that "Corruption is the abuse of state power for personal gain"[2]. In particular, this concept, which is frequently noted in the world community today, is defined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption"[3] as "corruption is the illegal use by a person of their official or service position for the purpose of obtaining material or intangible benefits in personal interests or the interests of other persons, as well as the illegal provision of such benefits."

Specialist B.I. Ismailov argues that corruption is a crime related to the use of official position for personal purposes. He puts forward the idea that corruption is often understood as taking bribes from citizens and obtaining illegal monetary income by government officials for personal gain in order to enrich themselves[4].

It should be noted that today in world practice, an appropriate legal framework and systematic practice aimed at combating and preventing corruption offenses are being formed. In particular, the adoption of the United Nations Economic and Social Council Resolution on Combating Corruption (1995), the International Code of Ethics for Public Officials (1996), the Declaration on Combating Corruption and Bribery in International Commercial Organizations (1997), the Convention on Combating Interethnic Organized Crime (2000), the Convention against Corruption adopted by the United Nations General Assembly (2008), and other international documents is of particular importance in preventing and combating these offenses. In particular, the Convention against Corruption, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly, is one of the most important international documents in the field of

combating corruption, which has been ratified by more than 130 countries of the world. This document reveals the essence of corruption and defines measures to combat it.

It should be noted that, taking into account its negative impact on the life of any state and society, resistance to the proper performance of the state's social, economic, and political functions, we can assess corruption as a threat to national security. In particular, in our country, along with the ratification of the above-mentioned international documents aimed at combating and preventing corruption offenses, the national legal framework and systemic practice aimed at combating and preventing corruption are being formed and improved every year. In other words, a solid constitutional regulatory framework is being formed in our country, aimed at preventing corruption, which is the decline of our society's future, combating it, carrying out democratic reforms in all spheres of state building and governance, and maintaining security and stability.

In particular, in recent years, a number of important organizational and legal reforms have been carried out in our country in the field of combating corruption. Systemic measures have been taken aimed at increasing the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, forming an intolerant attitude towards corruption in society. In particular, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption"[5], the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures for Further Improvement of the System of Combating Corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan"[6], as well as the creation of committees on combating corruption and judicial and legal issues in the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan are among them.

Also, today the prevention and combating of various manifestations of corruption in the socio-political life of our country is one of the important issues raised to the level of state policy and is one of the priority tasks of the activities of state bodies. In particular, on July 7, 2008, with the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the United Nations Convention against Corruption (New York, October 31, 2003) "[7] (No. ZRU-158), our country assumed international obligations to prevent and combat this offense, and also adopted the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating the Legalization of Proceeds from Crime, the Financing of Terrorism and the Financing of the Proliferation of Weapons of Mass Destruction"[8].

In order to increase the effectiveness of preventing and combating corruption-related offenses, create a favorable business environment in our country, and positively enhance the country's reputation in the international arena, and based on the tasks defined in the Action Strategy for five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the "State Program for Combating Corruption for 2019-2020" was approved in Appendix 1 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures for Further Improvement of the Anti-Corruption System in the Republic of Uzbekistan," and the updated composition of the Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Combating Corruption was approved in Appendix 2.

Also, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 No. UP-158 "On the Strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030"[11], one of the goals of the Strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" is defined as the accelerated continuation of work to increase the effectiveness of the system for eliminating corruption factors and the formation of an intolerant attitude towards corruption in society.

It should be noted that today, as in world practice, in our country, the solution of strategic tasks for the further growth of the country's economy, increasing the well-being of the people, improving the investment climate, ensuring the effective implementation of state policy in the field of combating corruption, as well as eliminating the causes and conditions of various manifestations of corruption require the adoption of new systemic measures. In particular, in today's rapidly changing world, the level of legal awareness and legal culture of citizens plays an important role in the fight against corruption, which is the decline of the future of the state and society. Because, by raising legal awareness and legal culture in society, it is possible to improve the system of legal education and upbringing, achieve a respectful attitude of all state bodies, officials, and citizens to the law and law, and increase the social activity of citizens. This, in turn, forms the basis of the fight against corruption.

World practice shows that if corruption among its bodies and officials in a certain state intensifies and develops, and if decisive measures are not taken against this situation in a timely manner, no matter how powerful this state may be, no matter how much underground and surface resources it possesses, it is a fact that its result will be not only an economic, but also a political crisis.

It should be noted that corruption today undermines public trust in government bodies in our society, negatively affects economic growth, hinders social justice among citizens, and leads to the disruption of the spiritual environment in society. Therefore, in the prevention and fight against corruption offenses, it is advisable for entities carrying out and participating in this activity to constantly implement the following practical measures:

- 1). Comprehensive study of the state of affairs in this area, as well as a systematic analysis of the causes and conditions for the occurrence of these types of offenses;
- 2). Taking measures to prevent and eliminate conflicts of interest in the social life of our country, primarily in the activities of state bodies;
- 3). Preparation of proposals for improving legislation and law enforcement practice in the field of combating corruption by entities carrying out and participating in activities to prevent and combat corruption offenses, based on the study of the best practices of foreign countries;
- 4) further increasing the legal awareness and legal culture of the population in the social life of our country, as well as strengthening an intolerant attitude towards corruption in society;
- 5). Organization of large-scale information and awareness-raising work in the mass media and internet resources by entities carrying out and participating in activities to prevent and combat corruption offenses, together with civil society institutions and the media.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the comprehensive, complete, consistent, and effective implementation of state policy to prevent and combat corruption-related offenses, which is the decline of the future of our state and society, will serve to increase citizens' trust in state bodies, the precise, timely, and objective resolution of issues within the competence of state bodies, and ultimately, the peace and tranquility of our country, the happiness and well-being of our people, as well as the sustainable development of our country, increasing and ensuring its international prestige and influence. In other words, the prevention and fight against corruption offenses are the key to the country's future

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